

Networks Analysis of Music Influence

Summary

This article analyzes the given provided data sets, and finds that there are certain relationships between different music genres. The characteristics of multiple genres are presented in the data set, through which they also have a certain influence on each genre and artist. We need to determine the significance of these features, the degree of influence and the relationship between each genre, and infer the promoting effect of each genre on the environment, social and scientific and technological changes.

For task 1, we build multiple directed music influence networks to compare, PageRank and reverse graph are introduced to simplify the formula and get the corresponding characteristic graph. We find out that Cab Collway is the most influential musician. For task 2, each attribute of different genres is classified according to the genre, and the average value of the corresponding eigenvalues of each attribute is obtained. Then, the variance of each genre is calculated as the sample of classification. By comparing the two, it is found that artists of the same type are more similar than artists of different types. For task 3, we use the Euclidean-distance-like measures to draw the influence chart. It is found that over time, the influence of jazz and country declines rapidly, According to task 2, we draw the similarity trend chart, for Pop/Rock genres, the similarity between features energy and instrumentality increased over time, while the similarity between features explicit and energy instrumentality decreased, while the similarity between other features did not change significantly. For task 4, we use the newly defined distance-vector, we get the all distance vector in a 400-node graph sample, speechiness was found to be the most infectious. For task 5,6, we used the full subset regression model for correlation analysis and prediction. At the level of $\alpha = 0.05$, the attribute that has the most significant influence on the popularity of each genre is obtained. According to the picture, in 1950, before and after the Pop/Rock genre number of artists began to rise sharply, fewer people have varying degrees of most other genres, from 1960 to 1970 years or so, various genres of the change of the number of steady, indicates that the development of various genres has been mature, until around 1990, most genres have reached the number of the extremum points, and began to decrease, this suggests that genres and even between the artist style between independence have been gradually formed. For task 7, Our works reveal the influence of music in different periods and identify the influence on all aspects.

Keywords: PageRank; statistical model; Full subset regression model; network

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1 Introduction

The background of this paper is based on the fact that different genres of music have an impact on different people or musicians, and we try to develop a method to quantify the development and influence trends of music. The development of music can be divided into multiple periods. As early as the ancient Romans, there were signs of music appearing. In the Middle Ages, music influenced people in the form of religious rituals, followed by polyphonic music in the Renaissance, Romantic music, and modern music. The 20th century is the rise of modern music, "music of the 20th century" once became the synonym of modern music. Modern music presents itself as a series of doctrines and complicated factions. Modern music shows its "departure" from traditional music with its disparate affiliations and eccentric innovations.

Based on an analysis of recent trends in music influence and the resulting data sets, we asked the following questions: Are there features from this data that might mark a revolution in musical evolution? Which artists represent revolutionaries or influencers of major change in your network? How to express the cultural influence of music in time or environment? Also, how to identify the impact of social, political or technological change within the network? We need to use the *full_music_data* dataset or parts of it to create a targeted music influence network and the two summary datasets of *full_music_data* and/or music characteristics to develop music similarity measures.

In this paper, we present a new community discovery approach based on PageRank algorithm to find these "important" users in a social network. Different from previous methods, we exploit prior knowledge of the given network, such as the mutual relationship between top 100 users in a community and the extent to which users are related in the data. In this paper, three indicators are required to balance each other in order to obtain the algorithm for community leaders.

2 Basic Analysis of the problem

1. For task 1, the question asks us to use the *influence_data* set or parts of it to create a (multiple) targeted network of music influence and describe what this subnet and its music metrics reveal. We define the influence factor function based on the data of influencers and followers of music genres, set the input and exit required by the data structure storage function, calculate the subnet coverage is about 0.902, and then calculate the ranking of the subnet and a series of data through PageRank

2. For task 2, the question asks us to develop a musical similarity metric using two summary datasets of *full_music_data* or musical characteristics. To measure similarity, the characteristics of each genre need to be analyzed for correlation. We think of an undirected weighted graph to make composition by weighting the characteristics of each genre. However, an undirected weighted graph can only simply reflect the relationship, so we thought of using distance distribution to solve the problem
3. For task 3, the question asks us to compare the differences, similarities, trends over time, and associations between different types. We can consider the similarity and influence separately, select a part of the data for analysis, classify and calculate the variance of each genre, establish the influence network with time attribute, and find that artists of the same type are more similar than artists of different types. Then the cumulative influence search function of the PageRank algorithm is established to obtain the influencer trend graph.
4. For task 4, the question asks us to indicate whether the similarity data reported in the dataset *data_influence* indicates that the identified influencers influence the respective artists. we use the similarity of the previous question and the newly defined distance-vector, we get the all distance vector in a 400-node graph sample, speechiness was found to be the most infectious.
5. For task 5, the question asks us to determine from this data whether there are features that might mark a revolution in the evolution of music, and which artists represent revolutionaries in our network we used the full subset regression model for correlation analysis and prediction. At the level of $\alpha = 0.05$, the attribute that has the most significant influence on the popularity of each genre is obtained.
6. For task 6, the question asks us to analyze the influence of the musical evolution of a genre over time, and explain how the genre or artist has changed over time
7. For task 7, the question asks us to show how models can express the cultural influence of music in time or environment and extend to social, political, or technological change.

3 List Of Symbols

Symbol	Description
G	A diagram of the influence of the network from the influencers to the followers.
V	the set of artists
E	the set of edges of G
v_i	influencer
v_j	follower
$deg^+(v)$	The number of people who influence other musicians.(out-degree)
$deg^-(v)$	The number of people influenced by other musicians.(in-degree)
$c_+(v)$	The coverage of the number of people influenced by an artist v
$c_-(v)$	The coverage of the number of people followed by an artist v
\bar{G}	A diagram of the influence of the network from the followers to the influencers
\bar{E}	A edge set of the influence of the network from the followers to the influencers
page	the output function defined by the page-rank algorithm
G_s	A similarity relation undirected weighted graph
E_s	The set of edges corresponding to the unordered pairs of vertices in V
Δd_k	The attribute difference function of between two given artists
a_{ik}	The value of the attribute k of artist v_i
σ_k	Standard deviation of attribute k
G_y	A diagram of network influence with time attributes from influencers to followers.
V_y	A collection of influential artists within a certain period of time
E_y	Edge set corresponding to ordered vertices in V_y

4 General Assumptions

Assumption 1. *The statistical standard of the data in a given dataset does not change over time.*

Assumption 2. *The degree of influence among all artists in the network defined by the model depends only on the link structure of the network.*

Assumption 3. *In regression analysis, the change of independent variable caused by other random factors obeys Gauss-Markov Assumptions.*

5 The Models

5.1 The Measure of Influence

we use the four given data sets to conduct data analysis, and find that the data is divided into two main factions, one is followers, the other is influencers, and each faction has different impact factors. Then, We need to build a social network. More specifically, our graph the influence network from influencer to follower, let G be the targeted network, which consists of a set of artists, denoted as V . To artists v_i , if he/she influence v_j , we add an directed edge in graph G , so the edge sets of G , denoted as E , is defined as $E = \{(v_i, v_j) | v_i \text{ influence } v_j\}$, Then we get the influence network $G = (V, E)$, For instance, fig. 1 shows a sample of 100 nodes graph. well look at the network G in more detail later.

Figure 1: A simple example of 100 samples

In graph G We can use the concept of out-degree, denoted as $\deg^+(v)$, to count influencers v influencing followers, similarly, an artist v_i is influenced by others is the value of

node v_i 's in-degree, which be denoted as $\deg^-(v)$. the simplest measure is to calculate the node's degree in the networks. However, if we erase some extra nodes, which have no connections with the observed node, the observed node's influence is bigger since it can cover more ratio of the network, but its degree has not changed. Therefore, we define

$$c_+(v) = \frac{\deg^+(v)}{|V|}, v \in V \quad (1)$$

as the coverage of artist's v 's followers, It can also be understood as the percentage of followers in network. In the same way, we define

$$c_-(v) = \frac{\deg^-(v)}{|V|}, v \in V \quad (2)$$

measure the percentage of v 's influencers in network. Futhermore, we also define

$$c_\Delta(v) = \frac{\deg^+(v) - \deg^-(v)}{|V|}, v \in V \quad (3)$$

For instance, we extract the nodes related of the Beatles to a subnetwork, we get $c_+ = 0.9505409582689336$, which means that nearly 95% artists of this subnetworks is he's followers, $c_- = 0.04791344667697063$, which means that nearly 5% artists of this subnetwork, the more followers one artist have, the fewer influencers one artist have, the artists have more influence, in out this subnetwork, the Beatles's $c_\Delta = 0.9026275115919629$, can measure his influence.

The advantage of this definition is that it is easy to study the influence maximization [3], so that the time complexity of calculating all the node's c_+ , c_- and c_Δ nodes can reach $\Theta(|E|)$, and the space complexity can reach $\Theta(|V|)$ if the data structure storage access is set, and the time complexity of re-query can reach $\Theta(|V|)$, which can respond to changes sensitively. This is a low complexity definition, but it only considers the direct impact, not the full reflection of the impact.

To make more accurate measurements, We need to think about the indirect effects, hence, we consider the indirect introduction of influence probability through PageRank algorithm (see [4] for detail) for processing, PageRank is a link analysis algorithm proposed by Google founders Larry Page and Sergey Brin when they built the early search system prototype in 1997. PageRank is a method used by Google to identify the rank or importance of web pages, and is the only standard used by Google to measure the quality of a website. The advantage of the PageRank algorithm is that it gives the global importance ranking of web pages, and the calculation process of the algorithm can be carried out offline, which is conducive to quickly respond to the user's request. Then we make some specific researchers on it, We go through the Bianchini's [1] literature, and subsequent studies on it made a lot of corrections, and we collected those changes. First, we

consider PageRank’s conditions. Based on two web page u and sets B_u and N_v , the average value of constant based web page weights of $R(v)$, we get the rank of a page u through the following simplified formula,

$$R(u) = c \sum_{v \in B_u} \frac{R(v)}{N_v} \tag{4}$$

where B_u is the set of source pages link to page u , and F_u is the page set u links to, N_v is the set size of F_u , c is a constant. we see that the R_u is an increase as the increase the sum importance of its source pages. It also implies that we see that the rank is additive.

Figure 2: the diagram of page rank’s graph structure and our conditions

Since there a lot of researchers make some modified of eq. (4), we need to make some modification to our graph to fit the theory(shown as fig. 2). In eq. (4), $R(u)$ can think a kind of probability of finally link to the webpage, it can be regarded its importance to the page network, In our influence network, we want to find who is the ultimate influencer and measure he/she’s influenced in the network. Hence, we introduce the diagram of the influence of the network, where edges are from the followers to the influencers, denoted as \bar{G} , $\bar{G} = (V, \bar{E})$, the edge set \bar{E} of the influence of the network from the followers to the influencers, by definition, $\bar{E} = \{(v_j, v_i) | (v_i, v_j) \in E\}$, and through PageRank algorithm to get a the artist v ’s influence index $page(\bar{G}, v)$,

Consider all artist v in artist data sets V , we calculate all $page(\bar{G}, v)$, then, we PageRank index of all artists in the data set. We sort the indexes and get fig. 3 which show the top 10 influencers.

Figure 3: Top 10 sorted by PageRank

5.2 The Measure of Similarity

Then we need to think the measure of similarity, Each creation feature of an artist can be compared for similarity to a certain extent. Therefore, for the eigenvalue of all attributes provided in the table, the similarity of the eigenvalue is compared respectively between and within genres, and then the final result of the two is compared, which can be used as the measurement standard of music similarity. Using the data set influence_data, match the genre of each artist in the data table data_by_artist, select the data in data_by_artist, Establish the undirected weighted graph of the similarity relation

$$G_s = (V, E_s) \quad (5)$$

where E_s is the set of the edges, E_s can be defined as

$$E_s = \{\{v_i, v_j\} | \forall v_i, v_j \in V\} \quad (6)$$

for any two nodes v_i, v_j , there is a node to indicated their similarity, the weight of each edge e_{ij} is the distance of two artists, denoted as w_{ij} , there is a function $w : E_s \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ to

calculate every edge's weight, the similarity can be measured by a Euclidean-distance-like forms

$$w_{ij} = w(e_{ij}) = \|e_{ij}\| = \sqrt{\sum_k (\Delta d_k)^2} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\Delta d_k = \frac{(a_{ik} - a_{jk})}{\sigma_k} \quad (8)$$

Where a_{ik} represents the k -th attribute of artist v_i , σ_k^2 represents the total standard deviation of each attribute. Although the attributes difference $(a_{ik} - a_{jk})$ have different units, we can uniform dimension by dividing σ_k^2 , then, all Δd_k have the same unit to measure the attribute's difference. eq. (7) calculate the total distance between two artist's similarity, the less w_{ij} , the similar between v_i and v_j .

Note that G_s is a complete graph, it is hard to calculate all the edges on a big scale, so we took 50 artists at random, calculate their distance, and at the same time, we recorded their genres. According to the obtained results, we make the following ???. The ??? shows the undirected weighted graph of the similarity relationship output according to part of the data, which reflects the similarity relationship between different genres. Each node color represents a genre of an artist. The darker the color of the line, The "closer" closer they get, the higher the similarity between them. To get a clear picture, we only reserve the top 5% obvious edges.

Figure 4: similarity relation undirected weighted graph

Through fig. 4, we can only roughly see some simple relationships. In order to more clearly show the relationship between genres and within genres, we calculate the distance distribution of between genre and within genre (shown as fig. 5).

Figure 5: The distance distribution of between genre and within genre

In fig. 5, Its easy to see that the distances within the genre are concentrated closer to the origin. So we can draw the conclusion that the similarity within genres is much greater than that between genres.

We get a similar conclusion from repeated sampling, which can be verified by continuous sampling.

5.3 The Analysis Based on Our Measure

5.3.1 The Influences between and within genres

To the analysis of influence, since PageRank index can additive based on our previous analysis we use the PageRank algorithm to calculate and sort the cumulative influence both within and between genres.

Hence, we selected the part of networks G_y , whose node set is E_y , the set of artists began active before year y . For every year y in dataset, We establish the cumulative influence search function established by PageRank algorithm:

$$page(\bar{G}_y) \quad (9)$$

Compare similarities and influences within and between different genres.

First, we analyze the individual in Pop/Rock genres. We selected the artists whose genre is Pop/Rock based on the data set influence_data. Then the data is classified at ten-year intervals to obtain influence data within genres for each decade. The top five most

influential artists in each period were taken as the vertical axis, and the years with ten years as the interval as the horizontal axis, to obtain the trend chart of influencers fig. 6.

Figure 6: Influence within Pop/Stack genre trend chart

It can be seen from the fig. 6 in the Pop/Rock genre started small number of artists, A few people have all the influence in the network, often within the genre on other artists produce the large degree of influence. With the passage of time, the influence on internal gradually reduced and tends to be stable, it may be that the increase in the number of genres within the artist lead to influence the average allocation, and probably because the increase in of other genres also lead to the music style of evolution.

In similarity way, similar trend charts can be drawn for all influencers of different genres in the data set of influence_data with a 10-year interval to discuss the trend of influence of the top 5 influencers over time (shown in fig. 7).

Figure 7: Influencer trend chart

As fig. 7 shows, the influence of genre jazz and country has declined rapidly over time, genre Vocal and Jazz gradually lost their influence, the impact of genre R & B suddenly rose and leveled off, the influence of % genre Pop/Rock rose sharply and kept growing, while the influence of genre Blues remained almost unchanged. The influence of all genres is stabilizing.

5.3.2 The Similarity between and within genres

To study the change of similarity, firstly classify the data of data_by_artist dataset according to genre, then classify it according to different time. In that case, we don't use eq. (7) to calculate the similarity since it needs to analyse the big scale data. We simply calculate the sum of variance of all attributes within each genre in each time period. Then calculate the average value of each attribute of each genre in each time period, and then calculate the variance of the average value of each attribute of each genre in each time period, and then get the change of the relevant trend.

Figure 8: Similarity within Pop/Stack genre trend chart

For Pop/Rock genres, as shown in fig. 8, the similarity of each musical feature of the genre changed suddenly to different degrees around 1960 as time went by. The similarity between feature energy, instrumentalness is increased to a certain extent, and the similarity between feature explicit is decreased gradually, while the similarity between other features has no obvious change.

Figure 9: Similarity between genre trend chart

As can be seen from the trends in the similarity of musical features between the different genres shown in fig. 9, the musical characteristic explicit has certain similarity between the different genres, but this similarity is irregularly diminishing, the similarity of most other musical features varies randomly over a fixed range.

5.3.3 Analysis of The Influence of Musical Characteristics

To see whether an influencer v_i do effected v_j , we need observe their edge e_{ij} , and we also need which characteristics influcing most, therefore, we need to know the similarity of every characteristics, we find the distance vector between any influencer v_i and followers

v_j , denoted by D_{ij} , Then we get

$$D_{ij} = (\Delta d_1, \Delta d_2, \dots, \Delta d_k, \dots, \Delta d_{13}) \quad (10)$$

Then, we get the all distance vector in a 400-node graph samples, and selected the most 7 closest characteristics between influencers and followers. as shown in fig. 10

Based on the outcome in fig. 10, we see that speechiness concentrated in the area closest to ground zero, in our sample, speechiness are the 'contagious' characteristics, and obvious, most characteristics are close to zero, which means the influencers do influence the followers, We also observed similar patterns in other sample sites across the network.

5.3.4 The Trends Analysis

As music genres continue to evolve, there are always relatively popular genres at different times, Besides, there are some obvious characteristics of each genre to reveal its evolution, With this as a starting point, we use the influence data set *influence_data* to match the data set to the genre. Using this data set for stepwise regression, at $\alpha = 0.05$, get the attributes that most significantly affect popularity across genres, and output each property corresponding to the p -value, we get table 2

Using data set *influence_data*, take the year as an independent variable the number of people starting a musical career each year The number of people starting a musical career each year is a dependent variable trends in numbers among the output genres, at different points in time, the changing trend in the number of artists influenced by each genre.

Figure 10: Comparative map of similarity of influencing factors

Figure 11: The changing trend of the number of artists exchanging between genres

In fig. 11, around 1950, the number of Pop/Rock artists began to skyrocket, most of the other genres have seen varying degrees of decline, it shows that the Pop/Rock genre developed most rapidly in the recent period. In the 1960s and 1970s, The trend of change in the number of genres in each genre trends to be stable, It seems that the development of various genres has become mature, communication-related activities are less frequent.

Table 2: The most prominent attributes and its p-value

Gene	Attribute	P -value($> t $)
Avant-Garde	instrumentalness	0.045256708
Blues	instrumentalness	0.003262299
Children's	acousticness	0.021727317
Classical	duration_ms	0.019467011
Comedy/Spoken	loudness	0.009975974
Country	valence	9.88×10^{-7}
Easy Listening	duration_ms	0.001 290 785
Electronic	valence	1.94×10^{-11}
Folk	loudness	6.23×10^{-7}
International	energy	1.93×10^{-5}
Jazz	acousticness	5.46×10^{-16}
Latin	loudness	7.41×10^{-10}
New Age	valence	3.93×10^{-5}
Pop/Rock	valence	1.34×10^{-64}
R&B;	valence	5.27×10^{-25}
Reggae	danceability	9.21×10^{-5}
Religious	acousticness	1.26×10^{-9}
Stage & Screen	valence	0.000 417 626
Vocal	acousticness	1.04×10^{-6}

In the following period of time, the number of most genres began to increase again, and by around 1990, the number of most genres had reached an extreme point and began to decrease, this indicates that the independence of creative style has been gradually formed among genres and even artists.

5.4 The Predict of Popularity

Consider the evolution of a piece of music, its popularity is often an important indicator, therefore, we correlated the average popularity of artists with other musical characteristics each year using *data_by_year* dataset.

Figure 12: The correlation coefficient diagram of each music characteristics and popularity

fig. 12 is the diagram of the relationship between them. Its easy to see that danceability, energy, tempo, loudness, acousticity and Instrumentalnes are related to popularity.

Taking into account the characteristics of the dataset, based on the average popularity of artists per year, popularity as a dependent variable, the average feature value of each musical attribute. We get that, Adjusted R^2 is 0.9752, F -statisticis 433.4 on 9 and 90 DF, p -value $< 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$. Found the two most significant musical attributes that contribute positively to the equation are danceability(p -value is 2.77×10^{-7}) and loudness(p -value is 1.00×10^{-5}). Using the fitted equations to re-predict the popularity of the data set, popularity, and rank the predicted values, table 3 lists the top 10 artists, the influencers of major changes.

Table 3: Predicted top 10 popularity artists

	Artist name	Predict popularity
No.1	Stacy Barthe	110.412970884493
No.2	Gossip	102.370504012434
No.3	Destructo	99.944805684796
No.4	Jonn Hart	99.6722632431294
No.5	Phoebe Ryan	94.6057349723894
No.6	Kat DeLuna	93.2539868594894
No.7	Matt Simons	91.7704716421929
No.8	Someone Still Loves You Boris Yeltsin	91.2109685881155
No.9	Katie Herzig	90.5219777625165
No.10	Feeder	90.3854506916791

6 Model Evaluation And Improvement

6.1 Strength

- The popular PageRank algorithm is well-known and constantly evolving and improving. The performance of this index can be optimized by the latest theories, techniques and algorithms.
- Sampling method can reduce the cost of calculation, and continuous sampling can improve the accuracy

6.2 Limitations

- The graph data information quantity is big, the algorithm complexity is high, may need more servers continuous calculating and summary results.

MEMORANDUM

To: ICM society

Subject: Exploring Evolution of music style, characteristics using Network Analysis

Date: March 17, 2022

Today network analysis becomes a widely used technology. After we process the given data to some networks, we give some analysis of the music evolution Based on Network analysis related model, theory, method, and algorithm, we can simply count the influence connects to reach a quick conclusion, in our work, we use the PageRank index to measure the influence of an artist using *influence_data*. We calculate all the artists' PageRank index, we can quickly find the top 10 artists, such as Cab Calloway, Billie Holiday, and so on. the index is a kind of probability that a user needs the page, in our music network scenarios, the index is the probability to be the ultimate influencer, hence, to calculate the genre influence, we can just add the artist's index and get the genre's influence directly. Today, Besides, we can easily select the data before a certain year, which enable us to observe the trends and other factors if we convert the given data set to the Network nodes' attributes. In our approach, We can relatively fast and efficiently calculate the influence index with more flexibility, that is, we can use the latest PageRank-based algorithm to adjust the searching method, the task can convert to the search information problems.

Another significant task to measure the similarity, we abstract the similarity as the distance, we define the Euclidean-distance-like index to calculate the similarity approach, After the calculate the similarity within and between genre, we find that the similarity within Pop/Rock is greater than those between genres. Furthermore, this measure also applies to music attributes situation. We can find the similarity in specific music characters between an influencer and follower, we find speechiness, liveness, and danceability can easily influence the followers' masterpieces.

Our method and analyze can easily be packaged and modularity, that is, in a much bigger data scale, you can calculate and store the needed data and make fast additions when the network is modified. It can continuous operation to deal with the BigData era's information. The network is extendable, can quick response to relations changes and easily add records. Using the network analysis method, data accessibility is better, even without other technology to handle data, users can get information from a small networks to find the information in some subnetwork.

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